

Temperature Dependence of the Ion Association of Valinatobis(biguanide)-cobalt(III) Complexes

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Conductivity measurement over a wide temperature range for electrolyte solutions can provide detailed information on ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions¹. The outer-sphere ion-association of some cobalt(III) complex ions with various anions have been investigated conductometrically²⁻⁹ but not including their temperature dependence. Recently, Yokoyama *et al.*^{10,11} studied conductometrically the ion-pair formation of some cobalt(III) complex ions with various anions at temperatures 0 to 50°. So far no studies have been made on temperature-dependence of the ion-association of cobalt(III) complexes containing biguanide as primary ligand. In the present study, conductivities of aqueous solutions of the chloride and iodide of valinatobis(biguanide)cobalt(III) complexes have been measured at temperatures 5 to 50° and ion-association constants calculated. From such data, entropy, enthalpy and free energy changes can be estimated which enable the nature of the ion-association to be probed. Using Bjerrum equation¹² and Stoke's law¹³, the respective sizes of the ion-pairs have been evaluated.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of association constant: The analysis of conductivity data was carried out in the same manner as described earlier^{8,13} assuming the following ion-pair formation:

(X = Cl or I) where triple-ion formation was regarded as being negligible in the dilute solutions investigated^{2-5,11}. The calculated ion-association constants for the complexes (chloride and iodide) are given in Table 1.

Ion-association and their temperature dependence: The plots of $\log K_A$ vs temperature (t) are shown in Fig. 1, where the minimum $\log K_{A(\text{min})}$ is found for each complex. The temperature-dependence can be expressed by equation (2),

$$\log K_A = P(t - t_{\text{min}})^2 + \log K_{A(\text{min})} \quad (2)$$

where $\log K_{A(\text{min})}$ is the minimum values of $\log K_A$, t_{min} is

Fig. 1 Temperature dependence of the ion-association constants between $[\text{Co}(\text{val})(\text{BigH}_2)_2]^{2+}$ and the monovalent anions, the (\square) chloride and the (\circ) iodide.

the temperature giving $\log K_{A(\text{min})}$, and P corresponds to the curvature of a parabola. Equation (2) was also used to derive the standard entropy and enthalpy changes (equations 3 and 4) for ion-association¹¹ in an aqueous solution,

$$\Delta H_{\text{ass}(\text{aq})}^{\circ} = 2.303R \{ \log K_{A(\text{min})} + P(3t - t_{\text{min}} + 546.3)(t - t_{\text{min}}) \} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta S_{\text{ass}(\text{aq})}^{\circ} = 4.605PR(t + 273.15)^2(t - t_{\text{min}}) \quad (4)$$

and the calculated values of $\Delta S_{\text{ass}(\text{aq})}^{\circ}$ and $\Delta H_{\text{ass}(\text{aq})}^{\circ}$ are shown in Table 2. The presence of t_{min} [$t_{\text{min}} \text{Cl}^- > t_{\text{min}} \text{I}^-$] was explained due to the weak hydration of the anion related to their structure-breaking properties. The increase of association constant beyond t_{min} is supported by increase of entropy changes. A positive entropy change has been explained on the assumption that the 'iceberg' structure around the cation is broken when association takes place leading to an increase in the degree of disorderness³⁻⁹. The remarkable increase of the K_A values before reaching t_{min} with decreasing temperature for the chloride and iodide complexes may be ascribed to specific short-range interactions¹⁰ between the amino-hydrogen atoms of the valinato

TABLE 1—ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS FOR $[\text{Co}(\text{val})(\text{BigH}_2)_2]X_2$, (X = Cl or I) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Compd.	5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°
Chloride	429.27	350.76	338.69	290.00	227.90	216.60	202.77	173.19	170.28	188.24
Iodide	376.66	332.97	293.76	288.00	266.60	233.61	194.30	195.19	204.05	220.88

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF [Co(val)(BigH)₂]X₂, (X = Cl or I) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Compd.	5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°
[Co(val)(BigH) ₂]Cl ₂ :										
$\Delta S_{\text{ass}}^{\circ}$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-56.15	-44.97	-57.71	-54.03	-23.53	-25.23	-38.56	23.65	-	52.67
$\Delta H_{\text{ass}}^{\circ}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-29.62	-26.85	-30.51	-29.61	-20.42	-21.11	-25.45	-6.01	-	3.19
$\Delta G_{\text{ass}}^{\circ}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-14.01	-14.13	-14.58	-13.78	-13.41	-13.46	-13.57	-13.17	-	-13.81
[Co(val)(BigH) ₂]I ₂ :										
$\Delta S_{\text{ass}}^{\circ}$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-65.95	-54.80	-52.21	-79.40	-113.50	-140.55	-	67.83	68.02	93.03
$\Delta H_{\text{ass}}^{\circ}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-28.43	-29.16	-28.61	-37.01	-89.03	-56.26	-	7.51	7.75	15.59
$\Delta G_{\text{ass}}^{\circ}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-10.10	-13.65	-13.57	-13.74	-55.21	-13.68	-	-10.78	-13.88	-14.45

TABLE 3—APPROXIMATE RADII (Å) OF [Co(val)(BigH)₂]²⁺, {[Co(val)(BigH)₂]Cl}⁺ AND {[Co(val)(BigH)₂]I}⁺ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

	5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°
	*S-B	S-B								
[Co(val)(BigH) ₂] ²⁺	4.26-	4.11-	3.65	3.45-	3.35-	3.25-	3.15-	2.97-	2.61-	2.49-
Cl ⁻	1.90-	1.68-	1.49-	1.30-	1.19-	1.08-	0.990-	0.91-	0.84-	0.78-
I ⁻	1.89-	1.66-	1.40-	1.31-	1.10-	1.08-	0.992-	0.91-	0.84-	0.78-
{[Co(val)(BigH) ₂]Cl} ⁺	6.36-2.33	5.88-2.00	5.25-2.00	4.90-2.12	4.59-2.42	4.34-2.03	4.05-2.00	3.80-2.02	3.56-2.36	3.16-2.14
{[Co(val)(BigH) ₂]I} ⁺	5.96-2.00	5.65-2.00	4.00-2.00	4.62-2.12	4.50-2.24	4.45-2.44	3.87-2.10	4.34-2.40	3.34-2.07	3.08-2.50

*S = Stoke's laws; B = Bjerrum equation.

and biguanide ligands of the complex and the halide atoms of the anions in the contact ion-pairs.

Evaluation of sizes of ion-pairs : The sizes of ion-pairs have been calculated following the method of Bjerrum¹² and Stoke's law¹³ and are compared in Table 3. Unfortunately, the two values do not agree well. However, such discrepancies have also been reported by earlier workers^{4,6,8,14}, with no proper explanation.

Experimental

The complexes, valinatobis(biguanide)cobalt(III) chloride and iodide were prepared following the reported procedures¹⁵. The complexes were recrystallised twice from hot water (conductivity water). The purity of the samples was examined by conventional chemical analysis and spectral measurements. The values were in very good agreement with the literature values. The conductivity measurements were made at 1 Hz with a Systronics 304 conductivity metre at 5–50°. Temperature was controlled with a Haake Messtechnik D8-6 bath.

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